

Artemisia afra African wormwood

© L. Siviya

Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.5 - 2 m in height

Distribution:

This species occurs across several South African provinces, including the Eastern Cape, Free State, Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, Mpumalanga, North West and the Western Cape.

Importance:

Artemisia afra is an important South African medicinal plant, valued for its reported antibacterial, antiviral and anti-inflammatory properties. Its assembled genome provides a valuable resource for future studies on the genetic basis of its medicinal traits.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 92.77 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 15.14 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 3.26 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.4% [Single: 76.4%, Duplicated: 21.0%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 618.25 kilobases

Contig number: 6 764

Sample Contributor contact details:

Molemi Rauwane

Nelson Mandela University

molemir@uj.ac.za